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for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy*

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1. Introduction

We live in a rapidly changing world. Technological breakthroughs in numerous economic activities have led to unprecedented progress, alerting European policy makers who understand that they have to fully leverage Research and Development (R&D) and Research and Innovation (R&I) in order their regions to thrive in the global arena. For more than a century, the idea of innovation-driven economic growth fascinated economists; as such, R&D and R&I have become important tools of the policy arsenal. At the same time, new challenges have risen. Innovation entails social, ethical and ecological dimensions that transcend economic growth and bring about new dilemmas. Climate change, nuclear power, biosciences, ICT, energy safety, public health, and economic crises, are only few fields in which moral concerns and public reluctance led to questioning whether R&I should remain unmonitored in the hands of scientists. Starting from the advent of applied ethics with the so-called ethical committees back in the '70s, the discussion evolved into debates on how citizens perceive and assess innovation and research. The aim has been to finally reach a point where R&I will be both socially acceptable (i.e. legitimate) and ethically desirable (i.e. morally correct) (Pellé and Reber, 2013; Panciroli et al., 2020; L'Astorina and Di Fiore, 2017).

In the face of these new challenges, the idea of responsible, ethical and socially legitimate R&I gradually gained impetus across dominant discourses. One of the main principles of the UN Global Compact is linked to responsible technology, since it advocates "*the development and diffusion of environmentally friendly technologies*" (van de Poel et al., 2017). Elements of responsible innovation are traced in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) introduced in 2015. For instance, the notions of environmentally responsible technological progress and social inclusion. SDGs stress the need for new governance mechanisms and joint actions by different stakeholder groups, which is central in RRI (Imaz and Eizagirre, 2020). At European policy level, the very term "Responsible Research and Innovation" (RRI) first appeared under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. The term was born out of the need of the European Commission's Directorate General for Research and Innovation to align the process and outputs of R&I with the concerns, values and expectations of EU citizens (Panciroli et al., 2020). Progressively, RRI gained prominence, indicating which pathways the EU R&I policies should follow in the years to come.

In this context, the report aims to engage citizens from the RRI2SCALE pilot regions (Kriti, Galicia, Overijssel, Vestland) in defining their views regarding potential future trajectories of their region, alongside with concerns and moral issues that might arise in relation to RRI. Approximately 2000 citizens per region have participated in our survey targeting specifically our pilot regions. Section 2 presents the theoretical framework upon which we have developed our questionnaire that reflects the main concepts of the project. Methodological issues referring to the data collection process and the structure of the questionnaire are given in Section 3. The main outcomes of this report are presented in Section 4. They act towards providing additional insights to WP1 tasks (T1.1, T1.2 and T1.3), and will help identify what are the challenges associated with: (i) citizens and societal engagement in designing open and inclusive territorial R&I ecosystems; and (ii) the factors associated with openness and inclusiveness in Regional Dilemma; and overall what are the (unstructured) Weak Societal Signals that need to be taken into consideration during the design of future R&I agendas.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Conceptualizing and understanding RRI

Currently, there is lack of consensus of what RRI implies, as the concept is still under development and a unanimous applicable definition does not exist (Schuijff and Dijkstra, 2019; Panciroli et al., 2020). Wilford (2018) describes RRI as an “umbrella term” that the process of R&I should consider towards assessing the potential impacts that it might have on several stakeholder groups. The most popular definition comes from von Schomberg (2013):

“[RRI is] a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products”.

RRI is defined by The Rome Declaration on Responsible Research and Innovation as an “on-going process of aligning research and innovation to the values, needs and expectations of society” (van de Poel et al., 2017). The EC Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2012) gives the following definition:

“Responsible Research and Innovation refers to the comprehensive approach of proceeding in research and innovation in ways that allow all stakeholders that are involved in the processes of research and innovation at an early stage (A) to obtain relevant knowledge on the consequences of the outcomes of their actions and on the range of options open to them and (B) to effectively evaluate both outcomes and options in terms of societal needs and moral values and (C) to use these considerations (under A and B) as functional requirements for design and development of new research, products and services”

In this respect, RRI2SCALE is linked with the wider tradition of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), with RRI building on the legacy of CSR (van de Poel et al., 2017; Gurzawska et al., 2017; Martinuzzi et al., 2018; Panciroli et al., 2020; Paredes-Frigolett et al., 2015). The connection with the even broader term of “responsible development” has also been recognized (Owen et al., 2012). However, RRI makes a step further. While CSR focuses on the later phases of the conventional life cycle of the product development (e.g. manufacture, use and disposal), RRI refers to the earlier stages of R&D, innovation and design. In our approach, the goal of RRI is that social, environmental and moral issues that may arise during the later phases of policy design have already been anticipated and integrated in the design process since earlier stages. In this way, unintended harms are mitigated or eliminated, before the implementation stage (van de Poel et al., 2017).

Another key aspect is the ways in which researchers and stakeholders should act in practice under the RRI framework. The lack of a single definition and its top-down perspective leaves this issue open, where standardised principles of RRI governance try to fill up the gap (Jakobsen et al., 2019). At the operational level, the European Commission has stated that RRI is founded on six principles: (i) ethics which means that research is morally accountable; (ii) gender equality focusing on equal female and male participation in R&I; (iii) public engagement indicating that innovation outcomes are aligned with the needs of ordinary citizens through public participation; (iv) science education where one of the goals of research is equipping citizens with expertise to more actively participate; (v) open access meaning that scientific results are accessible; and finally, (vi) governance referring to the fact that RRI principles are institutionalised as societal arrangements (Panciroli et al., 2020; L’Astorina and Di Fiore, 2017; RRI Tools, 2016).

Apart from these six principles, the literature indicates that RRI has four key dimensions: (i) anticipation: the capacity of R&I agents to foresee its multiple impacts; (ii) reflexivity: the capacity of R&I agents to critically reflect

on these impacts; (iii) inclusiveness or participation: the capacity of R&I agents to establish reciprocal communication channels with stakeholders and integrate their feedback; and (iv) responsiveness: the capacity of R&I agents to respond to social needs and new conditions (van de Poel et al., 2017; Wilford, 2018; Schuijff and Dijkstra, 2019; Gurzawska et al., 2017; Fitjar et al., 2019; Benneworth et al., 2019; Paredes-Frigolett et al., 2015; L'Astorina and Di Fiore, 2017). Sometimes, the dimension of transparency is added, referring to the open dissemination of anticipated impacts.

2.2 RRI, public participation and trust in institutions

Given that public participation is an essential element of RRI, it is important to understand what exactly public participation means, and why it is so important. After all, until very recently the mandates of what responsible and ethical research should look like were being dictated by experts in the form of ethical committees (e.g. lawyers, theologians, etc.). During the last three decades, however, there has been a shift towards a new paradigm of assessing R&I that strives for the inclusion of ordinary citizens. As public trust to the hegemonic discourse of experts diminished, there was a need for restoring legitimacy of public authorities, scientists and researchers in the eyes of citizens. Given that modern societies are characterised by normative pluralism, R&I must be able to accommodate the plethora of different, often conflictual, visions of what is moral, sustainable and acceptable in innovation. The goal is the creation of a “new social contract” between science, society and technology (RRI Tools, 2016). The idea of a reinvigorated social contract between science and society is supported also by Dijkstra and Yin (2019). It can be argued that what RRI simply does is navigating the concept “responsible” into a new phase of social contract. In the EU discourse, RRI became almost identical with fulfilling societal needs.

According to Dijkstra et al. (2010), public participation under RRI offers the “ideal” way to connect science and civil society and consolidates reciprocal communication between innovation providers and citizens. In this respect, participation must not be understood as merely receiving information and passively expressing opinion about decisions already taken (a posteriori) in the field of R&I. On the contrary, RRI envisions public participation as a process in which citizens are engaged from the very beginning – hence a priori – of the R&I design and implementation phases. Public participation in RRI refers to “upstream engagement”, under which citizens horizontally deliberate with governments and scientists on how R&I agendas can be drafted.

In the process of this “deep transition” from technocratic to participatory structures the dimension of trust is critical (Ribeiro et al., 2018). Trust can be understood as an interactive process resulting in win-win outcomes. From the side of public, there is increasing need for restoring trust to innovators, governments and enterprises, in the face of grand societal challenges, such as climate change and demographic shifts (Thapa et al. 2019). In general, trust to institutions is closely connected to the concept of a new social contract and public engagement. At the same time, from the business side, gaining the trust of public authorities and citizens can seal companies against potential backlash in the event of developing undesired technologies (van de Poel et al., 2017). In this regard, adopting RRI codes of conduct can enhance R&I organisations’ trustworthiness (Schuijff and Dijkstra, 2019).

2.3 RRI and EU regional innovation policies

Fostering smart, sustainable and socially inclusive growth is a key target of the EC Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy (DG REGIO). Traditionally, the EU regional growth policies were shaped by the dogma of “exogenous growth” that advocated large-scale public investments. This trend changed since 1980s, where policy makers started adopting new approaches, such as the entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP). The idea is that in less successful regions, coalitions of local entrepreneurial actors can jointly discover the inherent competitive advantages of their region, produce concrete action plans to deploy them, and thus, achieve increased developmental perspectives for their region. The outcomes of these processes should be the creation of local value

propositions, in order to increase the competitiveness of the regions within the complex and strongly globalized value chains network (Fitjar et al., 2019; Benneworth et al., 2019).

This approach led in 2011 to the development of EU Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3), with European regions being required to develop RIS3 strategies in order to request funding from European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). However, RIS3 strategies lack two important aspects. First, by focusing strongly on regional development, they sometimes overlook those implications that transcend the boundaries of one region (inter-territorial dependency). Second, they often (although unintentionally) neglect the moral aspects of regional innovation. This might result as an outcome that even though in theory the entrepreneurial discovery process supports stakeholder engagement, decision-making processes usually remain in the hands of regional authorities (Fitjar et al., 2019; Panori et al., 2018).

As such, RIS3 needs to be combined with RRI practices to achieve authentically inclusive, and therefore, promote smart growth. This can be done by adding the responsibility dimension and applying the four principles of RRI – reflexivity, anticipation, inclusiveness and responsiveness – in the core stages of the smart specialisation process. Regional innovation policies should be able to: (i) anticipate their potential effects on society, environment and regional competitiveness; (ii) include and accommodate different stakeholders' voices, even conflicting; (iii) reflect on their implications on citizens and adjacent regions; and (iv) positively respond to productive criticism from regional actors (Fitjar et al., 2019).

At the same time, the RRI discourse will also benefit from a meaningful merging with RIS3, as RRI currently suffers from a lack of concrete territorial conception, making innovators often overlook the local specificities where their activities unfold (Benneworth et al., 2019). Although RRI promotes the idea of horizontal dialogue between equal stakeholder groups, the questions of who these stakeholder groups are and on what scale the dialogue must be promoted usually remain unanswered. Even though regional innovation is triggered by "pioneer actors" who initiate interactions at regional scale, both innovation spillovers and stakeholder participation occur more frequently between co-located actors. Hence, it is impossible to successfully deliver RRI without combining these two dimensions -regional and local- and convincing stakeholders to foster innovation through responsible behaviour. Linking these two parallel discourses – RIS3 and RRI – can introduce an empowered holistic framework for regional and responsible innovation. Regional innovation and RRI are rather complementary rather than conflicting notions: the former regards cooperation between networks as key to development, while the latter adds into this process the obligation of coping with societal challenges (Fitjar et al., 2019; Benneworth et al., 2019; van den Broek et al., 2019; Rehfeld, 2019).

2.4 RRI, trade-offs and social dilemmas

Technological developments cause dilemmas, '*situations in which a difficult choice has to be made between two or more alternatives, especially ones that are equally undesirable*' (Ribeiro et al., 2018). Typical dilemmas are trade-offs between ecology and economy, or the fact that more inclusive R&I results in smaller innovation output (Paredes-Frigolett et al., 2015). RRI seeks to overcome these trade-offs by anticipating possible conflicts of perspectives, like the capacity of innovators to foresee potential impacts of novel technologies and mitigate repercussions (Ruggiu, 2019; L'Astorina and Di Fiore, 2017). According to the "Collingridge dilemma" or "dilemma of social control", the implications of a novel technology are fully revealed only when these developments have become quasi-irreversible, sociotechnical systems. This shows how challenging is to picture future developments to anticipate upcoming trade-offs through the application of RRI, steering the RRI discussion towards the principles of responsiveness and reflexivity (Ribeiro et al., 2018; Genus and Stirling, 2018).

At the same time, the “dilemma of societal alignment” has emerged on how to align technological developments with the needs of morally fragmented societies. RRI advocates public participation, but without specifying how this engagement can practically take place. The two complementary dilemmas – Collingridge and societal alignment – pose a double pressure on R&I regional policies (Ribeiro et al., 2018). On the one hand, innovators must capture and investigate public wishes into the early stages of innovation cycle, a process which is time-consuming and requires gathering of lot of information, given the complexities of the existing dilemmas. On the other hand, the tight time constraints in most cases have resulted in regional policies that leave almost no room for authentic, wide-scale citizen participation (Fitjar et al., 2019; Panori et al., 2018; Griniece et al., 2017). However, genuine RRI policies cannot exist without the participation of all stakeholders forming the quadruple helix (Carayannis and Campbell, 2009). Thus, ensuring citizens’ integration in regional innovation policies’ design and development is essential to promote RRI, as the societal benefits cannot be measured and evaluated in terms of mere economic benefits (Muhonen et al., 2019).

Therefore, the question becomes how to design regional R&I policies that can address both the Collingridge dilemma (lack of knowledge) and societal alignment dilemma (absence of social control) at regional scale, and mitigate inevitable trade-offs induced by innovation. The answer is not about predicting but aligning. Societal values must be considered early on, so even if technological developments cannot be clearly predicted, the innovation trajectory can at least be harmonized with public norms (Ribeiro et al., 2018). This can be achieved by effectively engaging local stakeholders through bottom-up social innovation rather than devising top-down policies.

In this context and given that R&I policies have a strong territorial dimension, local actors are the most appropriate stakeholders for formulating acceptable R&I agendas (Komninos et al., 2018). Local actors possess an intimate knowledge about the current needs, problems and hopes of their ecosystems, and as consequence they can help RRI policies become content sensitive (Panciroli et al., 2020). The concepts of collective participation, sustainable development and societal innovation interplay and can lead to multiple value creation, answering to different stakeholders’ needs. Participatory smart innovation can overcome unattractive trade-offs, because it is precisely only through innovation that opposite values can be satisfied through the internalization of environmental and societal values (Diepenmaat et al., 2020; EC, 2013). In this regard, RRI is an “open-ended” notion (L’Astorina and Di Fiore, 2017) that acknowledges the need to listen regional stakeholders, supply them with adequate tools of expression, and use their opinions for meaningful regional choices, paving the way for regional and responsible innovation models.

3. Methodological approach

3.1 Sample

The survey uses a sample including **7,683 responses from general public in 4 regions across Europe**: Galicia (Spain), Kriti (Greece), Overijssel (Netherlands) and Vestland (Norway). Data collection took place from June 2020 to September 2020 through 4 different waves – one for each region. Based on the conclusion of a consortium vote during the kick off meeting, it was decided that instead of resource intensive methods that would render data collection unduly expensive, to fill-in the quotas responses were collected through online panels by survey companies that were used for each region. As such, budget for data collection was distributed amongst the four supporting partners (Q-Plan for Kriti, RIM for Galicia, UT for Overijssel, and HVL for Vestland), which were responsible for finding relevant companies to perform data collection at regional level, since it was not possible to find a single company that could collect the responses for all regions. Online panel data collection processes were used for the cases of Overijssel, Galicia and Vestland, whereas CATIs were used for the case Kriti.

Supporting partners were also responsible for the translation of the questionnaire into the local language of pilot regions, with the aim to render the survey items and terminology intelligible to the broad regional audience. The concepts of RRI and regional dilemmas are perceived differently in each regional and thus cultural and socio-economic context. Therefore, upon collection of survey responses by the supporting partners, WR decided to keep the analysis of results at regional level rather than merging all data into a single database and resort to an integrated analysis, that would have ignored the regional specificities.

A more detailed account of the methodological steps about the survey execution is presented on Annex 2.

Apart from the core questionnaire sections (in more detail below), the surveys collected background information about participants, such as gender, age and activity status. Another key point was the categorization of responses according to the quadruple helix groups: (i) business (e.g. SMEs owners, entrepreneurs, CEOs), (ii) government (e.g. policy makers, civil servants), (iii) academia (e.g. professors, researchers), and (iv) civil society (e.g. CSOs representatives, ordinary citizens). Understanding the level of participation of the last category is particularly important, given that RRI in principle pays special attention to public participation.

3.2 Questionnaire structure

Based on the results from Section 2, that has identified the current state-of-the-art in terms of literature related to RRI and the Regional Dilemma, we have structured our questionnaire to get additional insights about these two notions for the selected regions. The descriptive characteristics of the sample and the distribution of the collected responses are presented in detail in Section 4.

Regarding the process of the questionnaire development, we have conducted a literature review and submitted a draft version of the questionnaire to the consortium, for peer-review and discussion in order to find a common approach for the insights that we aim to get from this task. The final version of the questionnaire reconciles – to the extent possible – the range of views and opinions from our partners and can be found on Annex 1.

The survey questions were clustered in 4 main sections, each of which corresponds to a research question. Each section and its rationale are presented briefly below:

1. **Section 1 – Identification of priority areas and future trajectories.** In this section we would like to get stakeholders' views regarding the most important areas for investing in their region. This will help us provide a comprehensive list of priorities to regional authorities based on their preferences. The second question aims at identifying insights about general public perceptions regarding future trajectories of the regions.
2. **Section 2 – Potential trade-offs between innovation and rising societal challenges.** In this section we ask stakeholders' opinion about potential conflicting aspects between innovation and rising societal challenges, such as negative environmental effects or exclusion of specific social groups from policy design processes
3. **Section 3 – Trust to local institutions and public participation.** In this section we want to explore general and institutional trust related innovation, as well as stakeholders' willingness to participate in regional innovation policy design processes
4. **Section 4 – Background information.** This section includes basic demographic information such as sex, age, country, place or residence (e.g., urban or rural area), educational background, occupational status and others.

All demographic information was collected in compliance with the general data protection regulation (GDPR) of the European Union and used solely for research and statistical reasons. In addition, to participate in the survey all research subjects had to fill-in a consent form that was included in the introductory session of the questionnaire. Finally, the management of datasets including such information adheres to the project's data management plan.

4. Analysis

4.1 Comparative descriptive analysis

4.1.1 Demographics and sample structure

The large-scale survey tried to capture the current state-of-the-art in four different pilot areas (Kriti, Galicia, Overijssel and Vestland), by collecting ~2000 questionnaires in each area. Table 1 indicates the final numbers of collected questionnaires.

Table 1: Number of observations by region¹.

Region	Observations
Galicia	2010
Kriti	2006
Overijssel	1660
Vestland	2007

In order to better understand our results, it is essential to perform an initial descriptive analysis of our sample for each region. This will provide us with all the necessary information regarding the type of stakeholders that have participated in our survey, alongside their demographic characteristics (age, sex, education level and activity). In this regard, Table 2 presents the overall sample structure highlighting that it is gender balanced in all regions. In terms of age structure, we can see that Galicia's sample is characterized by an increased share of persons between 25-34 years old (22.43%) compared to other regions, followed by a low share of 65+ years old group of participants (5.38%). At the same time, Kriti and Vestland indicate a very similar structure in all age groups, whereas Overijssel's sample has a high level of 18-24 years old participants (17.65%) and a lower participation rate of 35-65 years old persons (45.90%) compared to other regions.

When taking a closer look at the educational structure of our regional samples, we can see that the distribution between the four pilots shows some deviations. Although in all cases primary or no education covers less than 10% of our samples, secondary education in the case of Overijssel covers more than half of the collected sample (52.89%). At the same time, tertiary education shares, including both bachelor's degree and higher levels of tertiary education, are higher for the cases of Galicia and Vestland (66.50% and 57.45% respectively). The last demographic insight that we used for describing our samples refers to activity status of our survey participants. In this case, the majority in all cases refers to employed persons, which cover almost half or more than half of our samples (Table 2). Some particularities that differ between regions include the following: (i) high shares of unemployed persons for Galicia (16.20%) and Kriti (12.49%); (ii) low shares of students for Galicia (8.77%); and (iii) high level of persons with household activity for Overijssel (12.89%).

Table 2: Sample distribution by demographics (gender, age, education, and activity status).

Gender	Galicia	Kriti	Overijssel	Vestland
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¹ The data for the Netherlands were recruited via Newcom Research & Consultancy and the budget allowed for 1600 respondents to be collected. Additional data were collected via snowball method. However, these data were lost due to a technical issue with the data at the company and therefore, the final sample included 1660 respondents. With a population of 1,163 Million in the province Overijssel, a sample of 1067 respondents already gives a confidence interval of 95% and a 3% error.

Male	50.10%	48.31%	54.04%	50.12%
Female	49.90%	51.69%	45.96%	49.88%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Age	Galicia	Kriti	Overijssel	Vestland
18-24	5.93%	5.02%	17.65%	4.33%
25-34	22.43%	8.96%	12.53%	13.30%
35-65	66.25%	62.09%	45.90%	60.09%
65+	5.38%	23.93%	23.92%	22.27%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Education	Galicia	Kriti	Overijssel	Vestland
Primary or no education	2.19%	10.30%	9.58%	4.53%
Secondary education	31.31%	44.08%	52.89%	38.02%
Tertiary Education (Bachelor's degree or equivalent)	49.75%	34.93%	27.33%	33.18%
Tertiary Education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	16.75%	10.70%	10.20%	24.27%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status	Galicia	Kriti	Overijssel	Vestland
Employed	61.91%	47.91%	48.80%	62.20%
Unemployed	16.20%	12.49%	4.76%	1.65%
Student	8.77%	29.85%	21.45%	24.75%
Household activity	5.78%	4.28%	12.89%	5.10%
Retired	3.19%	5.27%	4.88%	1.60%
Other	4.14%	0.20%	7.23%	4.70%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Source: Authors' calculations

Finally, Table 3 gives us an overview of the types of stakeholders that participated in our survey. It becomes evident that the vast majority of are civil society stakeholders and individuals, covering most of the samples, specifically for the cases of Kriti (84.13%) and Vestland (94.37%). Another interesting highlight is that in the samples for Galicia and Overijssel we have high shares of stakeholders participating from the government sector (10.97% and 9.58% respectively), as well as the business sector (29.66% and 32.59%). For the case of Overijssel we can see that there is also an increased participation from the academic sector too (13.67%) compared to other regions.

Table 3: Sample distribution by stakeholder type.

Type of stakeholders	Kriti	Galicia	Overijssel	Vestland
Academia or research	4.98% (100)	2.89% (58)	13.67% (227)	2.39% (48)
Government	0.15% (3)	10.97% (220)	9.58% (159)	0.85% (17)

Business	10.75% (216)	29.66% (595)	32.59% (541)	2.34% (47)
Civil Society	84.13% (1691)	56.48% (1133)	44.16% (733)	94.42% (1895)
Total	100.00% (2006)	100.00% (2010)	100.00% (1660)	100.00% (2007)

Source: Authors' calculations

4.1.2 Priority areas and future trajectories

In this section we focused on collecting information about the regional stakeholders' views regarding the most important areas for investing in their region, in order to provide a comprehensive list of priorities to regional authorities based on their prioritization preferences. Moreover, the second question included in this section focused on identifying insights about their perceptions regarding future trajectories of their region. Starting from the first part of this section, Table 4 presents the findings for each region derived through the prioritisation question that was included in the our large-scale survey, where we highlighted the top 3 priorities for each region, so we can compare them. As it can be seen, support to small and medium sized businesses to develop and apply new technologies and upgrade of transport facilities towards making them smarter and more efficient, are top priorities for the three out of four pilot regions. At the same time, provide support to citizens and companies to use renewable energy sources by subsidising them is also a high priority for two of our regions (Galicia and Overijssel), whereas all other potential areas of investment constitute lower -but still high- priorities for the regions under investigation. It is interesting to notice that providing grants for R&I and creating new digital public services that are more easily accessed, both indicate lower than medium priorities for Overijssel (score less than 2).

Table 4: Prioritisation preferences based on stakeholders' responses.

Area of investment	Galicia	Kriti	Vestland	Overijssel
Provide support to small and medium sized businesses to develop and apply new technologies	2.55	2.71	2.58	2.21
Upgrade transport facilities making them smarter and more efficient	2.37	2.78	2.57	2.22
Support citizens and companies to use renewable energy sources by subsidising them	2.54	2.58	2.39	2.37
Provide grants for research and innovation activities	2.63	2.60	2.48	1.96
Create new digital public services that are more easily accessed	2.29	2.65	2.48	1.97
Skills' development through vocational training activities	2.42	2.61	2.61	2.12
Create new public spaces and infrastructures that serve regional specific social or environmental needs	2.30	2.62	2.14	2.27

Note: 1 – Low priority; 2 – Medium priority; 3 – High priority

Source: Authors' calculations

Moving on to Figure 1, through our large-scale survey we were able to capture existing differences between the potential future trajectories that stakeholders in each region have. Our results indicate that providing a high level quality-of-life to citizens, who are heard and participate in addressing their daily life needs, is the most attractive future trajectory in all cases, placing the citizen-centric vision at the core of policy design processes. Apart from that, the second most appealing trajectory for our regional settings includes their transformation into energy-efficient regions characterised by optimised energy production processes using renewable energy sources; which

comes close to the promotion of regions to also become hubs of innovative SMEs attracting highly-skilled workers. Options for potential future trajectories targeting a highly-digitalised public sector using citizen-friendly applications, as well as becoming a high-mobility region that uses smart transport for distance and time optimisation, are the ones that have attracted the lowest shares from survey participants in most cases.

Figure 1: Shares (%) between potential future trajectories in the four pilot regions.

4.1.3 Trade-offs between innovation and societal challenges

In this section the analysis will try to capture potential conflicting aspects between innovation and rising societal challenges, such as negative environmental effects or exclusion of specific social groups from policy design processes. This is an essential part of RIS3 policy design process and an integral feature for boosting participatory governance processes. In our survey, we choose to identify and evaluate potential trade-offs between promoting innovation and societal aspects related to citizens' well-being, gender inequalities, privacy and lack of skills.

Based on the results presented in the following figures, we can see that differences exist between the four pilot contexts, not only due to the synthesis of the samples, but also due to spatial specificities existing within each regional context. More specifically, in terms of citizens' well-being Figure 2 shows that both Vestland and Overijssel are more skeptical towards promoting innovation aspects (or policies) that might affect this parameter. On the other hand, citizens in Galicia and Kriti are keener on moving towards an increased innovation potential direction, even it might affect citizens' well-being aspects. It is very interesting to notice that 19.94% in Galicia strongly agree with the proposition that promoting innovation should be a higher priority than citizens' well-being, such as jobs, income, housing, health, safety (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Trade-offs between prioritizing innovation in relation to citizens' well-being (Q3_1).

At the same time, Figure 3 indicates that there is also a diversification in the case of trade-offs between boosting innovation and creating gender inequalities. More specifically, three out of four pilot regions (Vestland, Overijssel and Galicia) seem to be particularly strict when it comes to gender equality aspects, as less than 20% on the persons participating in the survey agree or strongly agree with the fact that innovation should be boosted, even though it might create gender inequalities in their region. This is a significant insight that should be considered when designing R&I policies based on the RRI approach.

Figure 3: Trade-offs between boosting innovation compared to gender inequalities (Q3_2).

Moreover, when the discussion comes to data privacy, the results presented in Figure 4 indicate that Kriti is the most reluctant region in terms of performing trade-offs between innovation promotion and personal data privacy (66.26% Strongly disagree or Disagree). This finding indicates that personal data privacy and security is a sensitive issue that needs to be treated appropriately in the region of Kriti when designing R&I strategies. Similarly, Vestland indicates high levels of reluctance (50.08% Strongly disagree or Disagree), whereas Overijssel and Galicia seem to be more open to innovation promotion and ready to accept some trade-offs for promoting innovation in relation to personal data/privacy. More specifically, almost half of participants (40.48% in Overijssel and 45.27% in Galicia) have agreed or strongly agreed that innovation should be further supported even at the expense of personal data privacy (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Trade-offs between promoting innovation in relation to personal data/privacy (Q3_3).

Finally, when trying to further expand our insights regarding the current situation in terms of potential trade-offs in our pilot regions, the final dimension under investigation includes aspects of potential lack of skills that might arise when introducing innovative sectoral changes within the regional context (Figure 5). In this case, Vestland seems to be more hesitant in accepting that type of interventions (34.49% Strongly disagree or Disagree). However, results from the three other regions suggest that there is a general positive attitude towards promoting innovation in this case. More specifically, Kriti has by far the highest score, with more than 2/3 of participants (70.27%) either agreeing or strongly agreeing that innovation should be prioritized over potential lack of skills. Galicia follows, with more than half of participants (60.77%) clearly opting for innovation outcomes; whereas Overijssel's position is also pro-innovation, since 49.52% of participants (nearly half) believe that innovation should be promoted, even if trade-offs in lack of skills occur.

Figure 5: Trade-offs between innovation outcomes and lack of skills (Q3_4).

4.1.4 Trust to local institutions and public participation

In this section we want to explore general and institutional trust related innovation, as well as participants' willingness to participate in regional innovation policy design processes. More specifically, Table 5 indicates the average trust levels to local institutions per region, as well as type of regional institution. Overall, there is a common understanding in terms of trust between our pilot regions, however, there are some significant differences when it comes to NGOs and large companies. As it can be seen, regional and local government institutions indicate similar levels of trust in Kriti (3.53 regional – 3.27 local institutions), Overijssel (3.30 regional – 3.31 local institutions) and Vestland (3.48 regional – 3.63 local institutions), whereas participants from Galicia seem to be more reluctant towards public institutions (2.79 regional – 3.08 local institutions).

At the same time, civil society and non-governmental organisations show increased levels of trust when compared to public institutions. The only exception is the region of Kriti that seems to have a significantly low level of trust in non-governmental organisations, which needs additional attention when coming to policy design processes. Moreover, universities and research institutions indicate increased levels of trust, specifically in the regions of Kriti (4.28), Galicia (4.17) and Vestland (4.10). When it comes to the business sector, trust levels seem to differ between SMEs and large companies, with the latter one indicating lower levels of trust. Finally, gender-balanced governing bodies show increased levels of trust, which are common to all regions, pointing out the significance of gender balance as a means to boost trust between citizens and public institutions.

Table 5: Average trust levels to local institutions.

	Kriti	Galicia	Overijssel	Vestland
Regional government	3.53	2.79	3.30	3.48
Local government	3.27	3.08	3.31	3.63
Civil society organisations	3.01	3.19	3.65	3.84
Non-Governmental Organisations	1.88	3.10	3.49	3.71
Researchers/scientists working for universities	4.28	4.17	3.63	4.10
Small and medium businesses	3.86	3.85	3.45	3.76
Large companies	3.11	2.97	2.88	3.52
Gender balanced governing bodies	3.64	3.33	3.68	3.69

Note: 1 – Strongly Disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Neither agree nor disagree; 4 – Agree; 5 – Strongly Agree

Source: Authors' calculations

In addition to the level of trust for specific institutions, our survey tried to shed light on the characteristics that play a key role for increasing trust in these institutions. More specifically, we investigated a set of four different action-driven elements that can be used by the identified institutions towards boosting people's trust towards them, including aspects of independent and multi-dimensional impact assessment of innovation, indication of their interests for participating in innovation, as well as open communication of their innovation potential. The results presented in Table 6 show that all of them are essential for strengthening institutional trust between different stakeholders, whereas open communication seems to be the most strongly acceptable feature for empowering trust aspects.

Table 6: Features and actions for increasing the levels of institutional trust.

	Kriti	Galicia	Overijssel	Vestland
Assess the effects of innovation in an independent way	3.38	3.40	3.67	3.28
Look at the effects of innovation from different angles	3.53	3.74	3.76	3.40
Clearly indicate which interests they have in innovation	3.68	3.72	3.72	3.50
Communicate in an open way about innovation	3.75	3.84	3.76	3.60

Note: 1 – Strongly Disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Neither agree nor disagree; 4 – Agree; 5 – Strongly Agree

Source: Authors' calculations

When it comes to public participation, Figure 6 points out that there is a strong agreement in all regions towards the fact that citizens should be strongly involved in the design and evaluation of regional innovation policies. We can see that there are no significant differences between these two notions and participants have similar opinion about participation in both design and evaluation processes in all pilot regions.

Figure 6: Perceptions on whether citizens should actively participate in the design and evaluation of RIS (Q6_1 and Q6_2). [Note: 1 – Strongly Disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Neither agree nor disagree; 4 – Agree; 5 – Strongly Agree]

Meanwhile, it is essential to investigate the level of previous participation in public dialogues to have a better overview of the previous experience related to participants in the large-scale survey. As we can see in Table 7, the level of previous participation in public dialogues differs significantly between the samples we have collected from our pilot regions. More specifically, Kriti indicates the highest level of previous participation in public dialogues regarding the citizens taken part in our survey (40.65%), whereas only a very small share of participants in the sample received from the region of Overijssel have previously participated in public consultation processes (13.92%). This is an essential information that needs to be considered when evaluating the results for each region separately, as it affects to a large extent public perceptions and overall views of public participation processes.

Table 7: Shares (%) of previous participation in public dialogues.

Region	Yes	No	Total
Kriti	40.65%	59.35%	100.00%

Galicia	24.98%	75.02%	100.00%
Overijssel	13.92%	86.08%	100.00%
Vestland	32.41%	67.59%	100.00%

Source: Authors' calculations

In addition to previous experience, our survey targeted on identifying the willingness of citizens to participate in future public dialogues related to smart cities, smart transport, and energy aspects. More specifically, Figure 7 - Figure 9 indicate that yearly and monthly involvement are the most popular answers to all categories. However, it is interesting to notice that for the case of smart cities a large share of participants from Vestland (49.11%) would like not at all to be involved in public dialogues related to smart cities. At the same time, we can see that participants from Galicia are more open in terms of weekly and daily involvement, followed by Kriti. Regional analysis in the following section will allow us to further investigate the specific demographic groups of individuals that indicate the highest willingness to participate in public dialogues, in order to provide even more meaningful insights to our public dialogues that will be implemented during our future project activities.

Figure 7: Extend to which survey participants are willing to be involved in future public dialogues related to smart cities per region.

Figure 8: Extend to which survey participants are willing to be involved in future public dialogues related to smart transport per region.

Figure 9: Extend to which survey participants are willing to be involved in future public dialogues related to energy aspects per region.

Moreover, we have collected insights regarding the potential means/channels for public engagement and their level of acceptance in being used as a means for stimulating participation in public dialogues. Figure 10 presents the results for each region indicating some interesting findings. More specifically, for the cases of Kriti and Galicia we can see that individual direct communication is the least popular channels for boosting public participation (19.66% and 13.37% respectively), whereas all other options are much more widely accepted by regional stakeholders. At the same time, participants from Overijssel indicate a preference in individual communication

(27.78%), online channels (30.16%) and open events (24.16%), reducing the importance of formal working groups. Finally, in the case of Vestland Figure 10 points out the effectiveness of open events organized by public authorities that seems to exceed all other means for public dialogues (32.22%). In this case online channels indicate the lowest share (19.51%) compared to other categories.

Figure 10: Shares (%) of channels for public engagement for each region.

4.2 Regional analysis

The following section provides a more targeted analysis of the large-scale survey results, focusing specifically on each region. This aims to provide more detailed insights regarding the main outcomes for each region, that could be used as valuable inputs to future project activities related to future scenarios and public dialogues. Each section follows a similar structure and provides all relevant information for each region decomposed in the various demographic groups that have participated in our survey.

4.2.1 Galicia (ES)

Starting with Galicia, we can see that the sample collected in this region includes 2010 observations (Table 1). The sample is balanced in terms of gender (Table 2), with an increased participation of persons between 25-34 (22.43%) years old compared to other regions. Moreover, there is a high participation rate from employed persons (61.91%), as well as unemployed (16.20%), whereas there seems to be a low share of students (8.77%) participating in our survey compared to other regions. Tertiary education is the dominant educational level in our sample (66.50%).

Regarding the trust levels to regional organisations, Table 8 indicates that in the case of Galicia there is a significant variation in trust between public authorities, large companies and other types of organisations. More specifically, in the first two cases the results show that there is a limited trust¹ as more than 30% of the survey participants do not trust public authorities and large companies at all or not to a large extent (48.56% for regional government – 36.49% for local government – 37.94% for large companies). On the contrary, results indicate that there is increased trust² in the case of researchers and scientists working for universities (41.87%), as well as small and medium businesses (24.78%). Medium levels of trust³ are recorded for the case of civil society organisations (69.34%), non-governmental organisations (62.16%), as well as large companies (54.74%) and gender balanced governing bodies (70.14%).

Table 8: Trust levels in regional organizations - Galicia.

Galicia	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much	Total
Regional government	20.89%	27.67%	13.21%	28.51%	9.72%	100.00%
Local government	15.25%	21.24%	15.50%	35.84%	12.16%	100.00%
Civil society organisations	6.33%	17.55%	33.65%	35.69%	6.78%	100.00%
Non-Governmental Organisations	9.97%	19.89%	28.36%	33.80%	7.98%	100.00%
Researchers/scientists working for universities	1.65%	4.44%	11.42%	40.63%	41.87%	100.00%
Small and medium businesses	1.60%	7.88%	18.89%	46.86%	24.78%	100.00%
Large companies	13.31%	24.63%	21.44%	33.30%	7.33%	100.00%
Gender balanced governing bodies	8.23%	8.47%	38.04%	32.10%	13.16%	100.00%

Source: Authors' calculations

In addition to previous results, Figure 11 illustrates the shares (%) of agreement (both Agree and Strongly Agree answers) for the four stakeholder groups, regarding the different types of actions that might be used from regional organisations to increase their trust levels in relation to innovation. As it can be seen, open communication about

¹ Limited trust includes answers: 1 – Not at all and 2 – Not much.

² Increased levels of trust include answers: 5 – Very much.

³ Medium levels of trust include answers: 3 – Indifferent and 4 – A little.

innovation gathers the highest strong agreement shares for most stakeholder groups (over 70% in three cases), reaching a peak of 75.91% for government actors. Furthermore, clear indication of the organisation’s interests in innovation and the investigation of the effects through various angles have also received similar positive opinions as means for boosting trust, specifically for the case of academics and researchers (82.76% for clear interests and 77.59% for innovation effects). Finally, assessing the effects of innovation independently stands out as a way for increasing trust in the case of government actors in the case of Galicia.

Figure 11: Shares (%) of agreement for different types of actions for increasing trust per stakeholder group - Galicia.

In terms of boosting stakeholders’ participation, it is essential to take a closer look at potential channels of engaging them throughout the whole decision-making process. Figure 12 elaborates on this and provides information on the channels that each age group prefers to be used as a means for strengthening engagement. As it can be seen, there is general acceptance of formal working groups, online channels and events organized by public authorities as common means for engaging stakeholders. However, individuals over 65 years old are more willing to participate through individual direct communication channels (19.43%), instead of using online channels (17.71%). This is of course expected, as older people are not so familiar with using online tools for communication, and even if they do, their influence on these age groups is usually limited. Thus, it is important to assess the potential communication channels that are going to be used for public dialogues to reach all relevant audiences in Galicia.

Figure 12: Shares (%) of channels for public engagement for each age group - Galicia.

A final aspect that we need to investigate for the region of Galicia, refers to the willingness of regional stakeholders to participate frequently in public dialogues related to three main areas: smart cities, transport and energy. To provide insights regarding this aspect, we explore the willingness of survey participants to be frequently involved in that type of activities. By frequent involvement, we refer to weekly and daily involvement in relevant public dialogues related to these areas. Figure 13 shows that for the case of Galicia academics and researchers are the ones that are more willing to frequently participate in public dialogues. Moreover, it is interesting to notice that the energy sector is the one that attracts Galicia’s stakeholders the most, in all different stakeholder groups, followed by the transport sector and having smart cities as last in the list.

Figure 13: Willingness for frequent public engagement covering smart cities, transport and energy - Galicia.

4.2.2 Kriti (EL)

Moving on with the region of Kriti, we can see that the sample collected in this case includes 2006 observations (Table 1). The sample is balanced in terms of gender (Table 2), with a low participation of persons aged less than 34 years old (5.02% 18-24 and 8.96% 35-34) compared to other regions. Moreover, there is a high participation rate from employed persons (47.91%), as well as unemployed (12.49%), as in the case of Galicia. In addition, we observe a share of students (29.85%) participating in our survey, which is close to the regions of Overijssel and Vestland. Secondary and tertiary education shares are very close (44.08% secondary – 45.63% tertiary), without indicating a dominant educational level in this sample.

Public trust in local institutions in the case of Kriti is highly diversified, according to the type of institutions, as we see in Table 9. The lowest level of trust is observed in the case of NGOs (70.23% expressing not at all or not much trust), fact which might indicate a more general negative perception of the islanders towards the NGO sector. Nevertheless, the rest institutions seem to enjoy relatively decent public trust levels. For instance, regional and local government institutions receive medium levels of trust (63.92% and 60.71% respectively), suggesting however that there is space for further improving the relationship between citizens and public authorities. The same applies to civil society organisations, with most participants (61.36%) expressing medium level of trust. Trust to large companies is evenly distributed, with medium level of trust being again the prevailing category (39.63%). It is interesting to notice that SMEs enjoy high or medium levels of trust (27.99% very much – 41.22% a little). Researchers and scientists working for universities receive the highest levels of trust, as a share of 51.88% of the respondents trusts them very much. This indicates a wide acceptance of research and academic institutions by the citizens of Kriti.

Table 9: Trust levels in regional organizations - Kriti.

Kriti	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much	Total
Regional government	4.78%	11.17%	30.35%	33.57%	20.13%	100%
Local government	10.84%	12.86%	30.76%	29.95%	15.58%	100%
Civil society organisations	14.82%	14.28%	35.34%	26.02%	9.54%	100%
Non-Governmental Organisations	55.48%	14.75%	18.39%	8.59%	2.79%	100%
Researchers/scientists working for universities	2.33%	2.89%	10.80%	32.10%	51.88%	100%
Small and medium businesses	2.50%	6.18%	22.11%	41.22%	27.99%	100%
Large companies	13.07%	16.29%	31.02%	26.30%	13.33%	100%
Gender balanced governing bodies	6.36%	7.31%	25.87%	37.17%	23.29%	100%

Source: Authors' calculations

Figure 14 displays the shares (%) of agreement (Agree and Strongly Agree answers) for the four stakeholder groups concerning the different policy interventions that can be leveraged to increase public trust levels. Communicating in a transparent way and clearly expressing the interests of stakeholder groups are the most preferred solutions, with more than 70% participants from civil society, business and academia and half (50%) of government representatives opting for these two policy avenues. Looking at the effects of innovation from diverse angles is also an accepted solution in Kriti, with more than 60% from business, academia and civil society agreeing or strongly agreeing with that policy. On the other hand, we can see that assessing innovation's effects in an independent way is a less popular option.

Figure 14: Shares (%) of agreement for different types of actions for increasing trust per stakeholder group - Kriti.

In Figure 15, our analysis focuses on how preference on public engagement channels is distributed in terms of age groups. It is revealed that online channels are the most preferred way, with age groups of 18-65 years particularly supporting online methods. Older people, who are not so familiar with technology, show higher preference for formal working groups and open events. Nevertheless, given the ongoing Covid-19 outbreak, policy makers should be cautious about engaging people over 65 years through open events, since they are the most vulnerable category. Formal working groups is also an accepted engagement strategy, particularly for age groups 36-65 years old. Individual direct communication, even though in general is not considered a strong engagement method, can be successful for citizens over 65 years. The general findings suggest that different engagement methods have to be adapted according to the age group targeted.

Figure 15: Shares (%) of channels for public engagement for each age group - Kriti.

Finally, Figure 16 shows the levels of stakeholders' willingness to frequently participate (on daily and weekly basis) in public dialogues for the case of our three focus areas (smart cities, transport or energy). Smart cities seem an important area of interest in the island, with more than 15% respondents from business and civil society to be willing to have a frequent engagement. With regards to the areas of smart transport and smart energy, only in the case of business sector more than 15% of respondents show eagerness for frequent engagement, suggesting that these two areas will concern mainly companies during the upcoming years. However, it should be stressed that energy attracts relatively high interest from academia, whereas respondents from civil society show equal willingness to participate frequently in smart energy and transport (with the latter having a slightly higher score, which can be attributed to the fact that transportation is an area that affects the daily life of ordinary citizens). Concluding, we can say that public engagement in absolute figures is quite low in the three domains, since no stakeholder group has more than 20% of participants willing to frequently participate.

Note: The government sector is not included in this graph, as there were no answers referring to daily or weekly involvement in public dialogues for these areas of interest.

Figure 16: Willingness for frequent public engagement covering smart cities, transport and energy - Kriti.

4.2.3 Overijssel (NL)

Our third region of our analysis is the Dutch region of Overijssel. We can see that the total sample accounts for 1660 responses (Table 1) and that it is balanced concerning gender participation (Table 2). In terms of age, the majority of participants (45.90%) are between 35 and 65 years old, whereas in terms of educational background, the majority of respondents have finished secondary education (52.89%), outpacing both participants with secondary education background from other regions, and other educational background categories within Overijssel. Finally, concerning status, 48.80% of participants in Overijssel (nearly half of the total sample) are employed, with students being the second largest category (21.45%). Participation from unemployed people is relatively low (4.76%).

In the next table, we focus on how the level of public trust differs across the type of regional institutions (Table 10). It seems that gender equality is highly prioritized in the region, since 24.46% of participants show increased trust and 62.28% medium trust to gender-balanced governing bodies. Large companies and SMEs enjoy in general medium trust levels: 64.76% and 46.92% respectively, although it has to be stressed that the percentage of increased trust is higher for SMEs (10.72%) compared to large companies (only 4.46%) indicating that public perception is more positively oriented towards the former. All the remaining institutions (regional and local government, civil society organisations, NGOs and universities) enjoy generally medium levels of trust. We also notice increased levels of public trust to civil society organisations (20.36%) and universities (20.78%). It can be concluded that in general, the level of public trust is decent in all the categories of regional institutions, which may be interpreted as robust social capital levels in Overijssel.

Table 10: Trust levels in regional organizations - Overijssel.

Overijssel	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much	Total
Regional government	6.14%	13.37%	36.20%	33.13%	11.14%	100%
Local government	6.69%	15.36%	30.72%	34.82%	12.41%	100%
Civil society organisations	3.80%	9.04%	26.14%	40.66%	20.36%	100%
Non-Governmental Organisations	4.76%	10.30%	31.69%	37.29%	15.96%	100%
Researchers/scientists working for universities	3.55%	8.67%	29.46%	37.53%	20.78%	100%
Small and medium businesses	3.25%	8.61%	38.31%	39.10%	10.72%	100%
Large companies	9.10%	24.28%	40.48%	21.69%	4.46%	100%
Gender balanced governing bodies	4.04%	9.22%	26.20%	36.08%	24.46%	100%

Source: Authors' calculations

Figure 17 presents how the share (%) of agreement for the different interventions that aim to promote public trust differs according to each stakeholder group. In the case of Overijssel, there seems to be a general agreement between stakeholder groups on what type of actions are most effective. Communicating in an open way about innovation is unanimously the most accepted type of action in all stakeholder groups (more than 65% in all groups). On the other hand, assessing the effects of innovation in an independent way receives the lowest scores from all the categories of stakeholder groups compared to other types of actions, thus being the least popular intervention method. The other two types of actions – i.e. indicating the type of interests in innovation and examining the innovation outcomes from different angles – lie in the middle. The results should alert policy makers in Overijssel on what strategies they could follow to increase public trust to local institutions.

Figure 17: Shares (%) of agreement for different types of actions for increasing trust per stakeholder group - Overijssel.

Building on the previous findings, it is essential to understand what engagement methods are considered most appropriate, and therefore effective, according to age groups. Figure 18 sheds light on this aspect and provides information on the preferences of each age group. In Overijssel, the general pattern across all age groups is in favor of online channels, open events organized by public authorities and other channels (engagement methods not stated in the questionnaire). On the other hand, results show that individual direct communication should not be considered by policy makers, as it is clearly the least preferred category for all age groups. Formal working groups could work for people over 65 years and between 18 and 24 years. We can conclude that there is consensus between age groups about engagement methods, with subtle diversifications.

Figure 18: Shares (%) of channels for public engagement for each region - Overijssel.

As in the previous analyses (Galicia and Kriti), Figure 19 examines the level of willingness for frequent public engagement (once again, frequent engagement means daily and weekly participation) per stakeholder group in the three different areas of smart cities, smart transport and smart energy. Overall, participants from government and academia/research appear to be the most willing to engage themselves on a frequent basis in all the three areas of interest (more than 10% in all areas) as compared to business and civil society. The latter show inertia concerning frequent participation, especially in the field of transport; this should be taken into consideration by policy makers. In terms of the areas of interest per se, smart energy attracts the most positive responses from government, business and civil society, while academia or research participants show stronger interest in smart transport.

Figure 19: Willingness for frequent public engagement covering smart cities, transport and energy - Overijssel.

4.2.4 Vestland (NO)

The Norwegian region of Vestland is the last part of our regional analysis. The sample consists of 2007 participants (Table 1), achieving an almost perfect gender balance (50.12% men and 49.88% women). Table 2 shows that participants between 35- and 65-years old account for 60.09% of the sample, with people over 65 years being the second largest category (22.27%). Regarding the educational background of participants, most of them (38.02%) had finished secondary education, whereas participants from Tertiary Education (Bachelor's degree or equivalent) is the second largest group (33.18%). When we examine the status of participants, employed persons form more than half of the sample (62.20%), whereas students are at the second place, almost covering one fourth of the sample (24.75%).

Moving on to .

Table 11 that displays the levels of trust (low, medium or increased) to the regional organizations, we can notice that, as compared to the other three regions, the share of participants who express low trust level is exceptionally low in all categories in institutions. Only in the case of regional government institutions more than 5% of respondents show low trust levels. On the other hand, research/scientists working for universities, NGOs and civil society organisations present high shares of increased trust: 33.40%, 20.29% and 19.60% respectively. This may indicate that the relationship between the general public with universities and NGOs/CSOs is quite strong. The rest of institutions show, on average, medium trust levels, with no noticeable exceptions. Overall, institutions seem to be positively perceived by citizens in Vestland.

Table 11: Trust levels in regional organizations - Vestland

Vestland	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much	Total
Regional government	5.41%	16.38%	15.87%	49.49%	12.86%	100%
Local government	3.50%	13.48%	14.75%	52.66%	15.61%	100%
Civil society organisations	1.23%	6.80%	18.86%	52.84%	20.29%	100%
Non-Governmental Organisations	4.00%	9.37%	17.48%	49.54%	19.60%	100%
Researchers/scientists working for universities	1.52%	3.79%	11.47%	49.82%	33.40%	100%
Small and medium businesses	0.81%	4.27%	24.64%	58.89%	11.38%	100%
Large companies	2.13%	10.82%	27.17%	52.41%	7.47%	100%
Gender balanced governing bodies	1.59%	2.92%	33.56%	48.46%	13.47%	100%

Source: Authors' calculations

Figure 20 presents how different stakeholder groups that participated in the survey select different types of actions that aim to increase trust levels. All four stakeholder groups express unanimously strong preference (more than 55%) in favor of clearly indicating which interests they have in innovation as a strategy to foster institutional trust. Communication in an open way about innovation seems to be supported by civil society, business and academia (more than 50% in all) but is very low among government representatives. The last two types of actions – i.e. monitoring innovation's effects from different angles and assessing these effects independently – are not strongly supported by stakeholder groups, with the only exception of academia.

Figure 20: Shares (%) of agreement for different types of actions for increasing trust per stakeholder group - Vestland.

Making a step further, the next part of our analysis focuses on what public engagement channels are the most appropriate per age group. Figure 21 summarizes visually the results. It seems that open events organized by public authorities is the most preferred engagement strategy, in particular among people between 35-65 years and 65+ years old. However, cautious is needed, since many people coming from these age groups are usually part of the most vulnerable population segments concerning Covid-19. Formal working groups is also accepted by all age groups, with young people (18-24 years old) clearly supporting them. Finally, online channels, especially during the

current pandemic, can be leveraged as an effective alternative, since they are preferred by younger age groups, with the preference share progressively decreasing as the age group increases.

Figure 21: Shares (%) of channels for public engagement for each region - Vestland.

The last part of our regional analysis on Vestland regards the willingness for frequent (daily and weekly basis) public engagement from each stakeholder group in the domains of smart cities, transport and energy. As we can see in Figure 22, government representatives in Vestland is the most mobilized group, with more than 55% of respondents wishing frequent engagement in smart transport and more than 45% in smart energy. All other stakeholder groups seem to be quite reluctant in frequently participating in the three domains. However, a more careful examination of results reveals that smart transport and smart energy gain relatively more positive answers on frequent engagement from all stakeholder groups as compared to smart cities. This may be indicative of the most debated regional dilemmas that Vestland will be dealing with during the upcoming years.

Figure 22: Willingness for frequent public engagement covering smart cities, transport and energy - Vestland.

5. Summary of key findings

This section provides an overview of the key findings that the survey results have revealed. These findings can help us understand the main trade-offs and prioritisation areas for each region related to R&I policies, and potential ways for building and strengthening participation and engagement to increase stakeholders' interest in R&I policies. All these inputs can be used to empower future public dialogues' acceptance and effectiveness, which will be implemented with the regional targeted workshops in the next steps of the project. Combining the results of all these activities can help regional authorities to develop more informed policy recommendations and updated strategic plans and interventions, helping to achieve a wider uptake of the RRI aspects across Europe.

Results have shown that in terms of prioritisation, **providing support to small and medium sized businesses (SMEs) towards developing and applying new technologies**, together with **upgrading transport facilities by making them smarter and more efficient**, are the **two most commonly retrieved high priorities** between our pilot regions. In relation to this, providing support to citizens and companies to use renewable energy sources by subsidising them is also a high priority for two of our regions (Galicia and Overijssel).

With regard to future trajectories and vision building for each region, the survey participants have indicated that **providing a high level quality-of-life to citizens is the most attractive future trajectory** in all cases, placing the citizen-centric vision at the core of policy design processes. Moreover, **transforming regions into energy-efficient areas characterised by optimised energy production processes using renewable energy sources**, as well as **promoting regions to become hubs of innovative SMEs attracting highly skilled workers**, are **two additional trajectories** that are widely accepted.

Identifying trade-offs between innovation and grand societal challenges is another aspect into which this survey tries to shed light. Our results indicate that **stakeholders are highly skeptical in cases where promoting innovation aspects (or policies) might affect citizens' well-being**, as well as in the case of **trade-offs between boosting innovation and creating gender inequalities**. At the same time, there is a significant diversification of results between regions in terms of assessing trade-offs between innovation promotion and personal data privacy. This finding indicates that **personal data privacy and security is a sensitive issue** that needs to be treated appropriately in the region of Kriti, whereas it is not a key aspect in all other pilot regions. The only case where survey participants have not been found to be highly skeptical refers to aspects of potential lack of skills that might arise when introducing innovative sectoral changes within the regional context.

The results also provide some significant findings related to trust in the regional institutional framework. More specifically, **civil society, SMEs and non-governmental organisations show increased levels of trust**, when compared to public institutions, such as local and regional authorities. In relation to specific features that could be adopted by institutions for empowering trust towards them, **open communication seems to be the most strongly acceptable feature**. Yearly and monthly involvement are the most popular answers regarding stakeholders' willingness to participate in public dialogues related to our three focus areas (smart cities, transport and energy).

Finally, when it comes to **communication channels** there are some **diversifications between regions**. Kriti and Galicia point out online channels as more attractive way for boosting communication with regional stakeholders, whereas the indicate individual direct communication as the least popular channel. However, participants in Vestland and Overijssel point out the effectiveness of individual direct communication and open events organized by public authorities, which seems to exceed all other means for public dialogues in Vestland.

The analysis offered us also the opportunity to investigate some interesting characteristics regarding each pilot case separately. In this regard, we have identified the main attitudes towards regional priorities, potential future

trajectories, and innovation trade-offs in the 4 pilot regions. Overall, we have seen that, generally, **there is a common approach** towards these aspects, as well as potential stakeholder engagement in all cases. Moreover, it was possible to provide additional information regarding the main channels of public engagement that participants wanted to have in each region, based on their age group. In terms of participation, we can say that **some variations have been found between the pilot regions**, as in some of them survey participants wanted to focus more on transport and energy, whereas in some others their main focus was on smart cities.

Overall, the insights in this report offer a comprehensive descriptive overview of the general regional trends in terms of setting priorities and level of trade-offs between innovation and grand societal challenges that might exist within each region. They **provide a concrete starting point for discussion and design of the future public dialogues** that will be implemented in the next steps of the project.

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Annex I: Survey Questionnaire

Welcome note

Dear participant, welcome to our survey!

The survey lasts about 5 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers, this is about your views. All data is anonymised, and your privacy is guaranteed.

Thank you very much in advance for your support, which is very much appreciated!

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us via rri2scale@apre.it

Best wishes,

The RRI2SCALE team

What is the RRI2SCALE project?

RRI2SCALE aims to provide a method to support regional Research & Innovation (R&I) systems to effectively meet the requirements and needs of their regional actors. To this end, the project will identify the level of integration of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) framework in four EU regions and the basic elements of their regional R&I ecosystems. The focus is to promote dialogue to understand citizens' perceptions regarding research and innovation dilemmas that might exist in these regions. The following questions are based on the RRI framework and serve to assess stakeholders' techno-moral attitudes regarding technological change and socio-economic outcomes.

SECTION 0 – ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Before proceeding, we would like to kindly draw your attention to the following information:

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may refuse to take part. Please be aware that if you do decide to participate, you may also stop participating at any time without penalty. There are 10 questions in this survey related to Responsible Research and Innovation, including processes or concerns in your region.

BENEFITS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating. However, your responses may help us to improve our RRI2SCALE project.

RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this survey. By answering the questionnaire, you grant permission for the data generated from this questionnaire to be used ONLY for research purposes. The results will be disseminated in scientific publications and public reports wherein anonymity will be guaranteed. Regarding the dissemination plans, you can find more details via the following link www.rri2scale.eu. Participants' utterances will be used in reports as quotes, but in such a way that anonymity is ensured. To sum up, any information provided remains ANONYMOUS!

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your survey answers and data will be stored in a password-protected electronic format. We do not collect any identifying information, such as your name, email address, or IP address. Therefore, your responses will remain anonymous. No one will be able to identify you or your answers, and no one will know whether you participated in the study.

CONTACT

If you have questions at any time about the study or the procedures, you may contact our project coordinator via email at rri2scale@apre.it

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below.

Clicking on the “Agree” button indicates that:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ You have read the above information. ✓ You are clearly informed. ✓ You voluntarily agree to participate. ✓ Your anonymous answers can be used for research purposes. ✓ You are 18 years of age or older. 	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree
--	--------------------------------

Before starting, we would like to give you a simple definition of innovation that we use for this survey. More specifically, we refer to innovation as a set of new technologies and forms of organisation that reshape regional activities. It may include new digital services in various areas (e.g. transport or smart cities), as well as community activities that result in more effective collaborative actions (e.g. recycling or energy production).

SECTION 1 – IDENTIFICATION OF PRIORITY AREAS AND FUTURE TRAJECTORIES

In this section we would like to get your views regarding the most important areas for investing in your region. This will help us provide a comprehensive list of priorities to regional authorities based on your preferences. The second question aims at identifying insights about your perceptions regarding future trajectories of your region.

1. In the following list, please indicate which areas you would choose your region to spend money on.

	Low Priority	Medium Priority	High Priority
Q1_1 Provide grants for research and innovation activities			
Q1_2 Provide support to small and medium sized businesses to develop and apply new technologies			
Q1_3 Support citizens and companies to use renewable energy sources by subsidising them			
Q1_4 Create new digital public services that are more easily accessed			
Q1_5 Upgrade transport facilities making them smarter and more efficient (rail, road, or airports)			
Q1_6 Skills' development through vocational training activities			
Q1_7 Create new public spaces and infrastructures that serve regional specific social or environmental needs			
Q1_8 Other (Please specify: _____)			

2. In the long-run, I believe that my region should be mainly shaped as (max two options):

- Q2_1 a hub of innovative small and medium sized businesses that will attract highly skilled workers
- Q2_2 a highly-digitalised public sector region that uses citizen-friendly applications
- Q2_3 an energy-efficient region characterised by optimised energy production processes using renewable energy sources
- Q2_4 a high-mobility region that uses smart transport for optimising access, distances and time
- Q2_5 a high quality of life region where citizens are heard and participate in addressing their daily life needs

SECTION 2 - POTENTIAL TRADE-OFFS BETWEEN INNOVATION AND RISING SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

In this section we ask your opinion about potential conflicting aspects between innovation and rising societal challenges, such as negative environmental effects or exclusion of specific social groups from policy design processes.

3. Please indicate your agreement with the following arguments:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Q3_1 I believe that promoting innovation should be a higher priority than citizens' well-being (such as jobs, income, housing, health, safety).					
Q3_2 I believe that innovation should be boosted even though it might create gender inequalities in my region.					
Q3_3 I believe that it is good to support innovation when it has positive impact on smart cities, energy, and transport, even if it requires access to my personal data.					
Q3_4 I believe that innovation outcomes for facilitating smart cities, energy and transport should be boosted, even if I might not have all the necessary skills to use them.					

SECTION 3 - TRUST TO LOCAL INSTITUTIONS AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

In this section we want to explore general and institutional trust related innovation, as well as your willingness to participate in regional innovation policy design processes.

4. In terms of general trust, I trust organizations or groups of people when they:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Q4_1 assess the effects of innovation in an independent way					
Q4_2 look at the effects of innovation from different angles					
Q4_3 clearly indicate which interests they have in innovation					
Q4_4 communicate in an open way about innovation					

5. Please indicate to what extent you trust the following organisations in your region.

	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much
Q5_1 Regional government					
Q5_2 Local government					
Q5_3 Civil society organisations					

Q5_4 Non-Governmental Organisations					
Q5_5 Researchers/scientists working for universities					
Q5_6 Small and medium businesses					
Q5_7 Large companies					
Q5_8 Gender balanced governing bodies					

6. Please indicate your agreement with the following arguments:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Q6_1 I believe that citizens should be actively involved in helping to design regional innovation policies					
Q6_2 I believe that citizens should be actively involved in helping to evaluate regional innovation policies					

7. Which of the following ways would you choose if you wanted to get involved in public dialogues? (max 2)

- Q7_1 individual direct communication (e.g. individual meetings, letters etc.)
- Q7_2 online channels (e.g. platforms, social media accounts etc.)
- Q7_3 formal working groups (online and live) representing a community or group
- Q7_4 open events organized by public authorities (e.g. workshops)
- Q7_5 Other (Please specify: _____)

8. Q8 Have you ever been involved in public dialogues?

- Yes
- No

9. To what extend are you willing to be involved in future public dialogues related to:

	Not at all	Yearly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
Q9_1 smart cities					
Q9_2 transport					
Q9_3 energy					

SECTION 4 – BACKGROUND INFORMATION

10. Q10 Gender:

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to mention

11. Q11 Age group:

- 18 – 24 years old
- 25 – 34 years old
- 35 – 65 years old
- More than 65 years old

12. Q12 Please indicate your educational level:

- No or Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education (Bachelor's degree or equivalent)
- Higher education (Master's, PhD or equivalent)

13. Q13 Please indicate your activity status:

- Employed
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Student
- Household activities
- Other

14. Q14 You participate in this survey as part of:

- Academia or research
- Government
- Business
- Civil Society

15. Q15 Do you have any additional comments you would like to include? (optional)

16. Q16 I want to be informed about the survey results and future RRI2SCALE activities (optional)

- Yes
- No

Contact email (please insert the email where you wish to receive our future updates): _____

- I do consent to receive newsletters and updates from the RRI2SCALE project.

Survey end

Thank you for taking part into this survey and contributing to our understanding of what people think about Responsible Research and Innovation!

Your input will help us a great deal to identify key elements and perceptions that should be considered during the implementation of our project.

Do you have any questions or comments? You can contact us at rri2scale@apre.it

Feel free to follow RRI2SCALE social media accounts to stay in touch and check our website for more information!

www.rri2scale.eu

Facebook: RRI2Scale Project

Twitter: @rri2scale

Linkedin: RRI2SCALE Project

Youtube: RRI2SCALE Project

Informed consent

This privacy policy details information collection practices related to your personal data and other related information and the limited manner in which the RRI2SCALE project will use and disclose the information provided to us when you responded the survey.

By participating in the survey, you voluntarily consent to the collection and use of your information by RRI2SCALE as set forth in this privacy policy. If you have any questions concerning this privacy policy or our data collection practices you may contact us at info@white-research.eu. We reserve the right to change this privacy policy at any time and inform all participants about the updates.

In addition to your opinion, we are collecting some personal information such as age, country of residence and educational status for socio-demographic purposes. The collected data will be saved and used until the end of the research period of the RRI2SCALE project. The data will be only used for the purpose of the RRI2SCALE, funded under the European Union Horizon 2020 program, aiming to promote Responsible Research and Innovation principles for Regional Innovation Policies across Europe.

The lawfulness of the processing of personal data is determined pursuant to Article 6 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With respect to personal data, the processing of personal data is based on consent.

Annex II: Methodological note on the survey

Annex 2 presents the main steps followed under T1.4 for developing, conducting and analyzing the large-scale survey. This process included four discrete steps: (i) questionnaire development, (ii) data collection, (iii) data analysis, and (iv) overall discussion of the findings.

Step 1 – Questionnaire development

White Research (WR) was responsible for developing the questionnaire for the survey. The aim of this process was to develop a questionnaire focusing on capturing the regional dilemmas based on the RRI principles through input provided by the general public from the four pilot regions. To this end, the main challenge of this process was to effectively translate the scientific language of RRI and innovation policy into concrete and intelligible questions for citizens. To address this challenge, we conducted several discussion-rounds with all consortium partners, including also the pilot regions, focusing on finding a good balance between the scientific perspective of the project and the clear statement of the questions included in the survey. The received inputs and comments were eventually encompassed in the final version of the questionnaire – as presented in Annex 1 of the present document – making it easily understood by a broad audience. The final structure of the questionnaire is presented in Section 3.2.

The final version of the questionnaire was then translated in the pilots' four local languages by the supporting partners: (i) Q-Plan for Kriti; (ii) UT for Overijssel; (iii) RIM for Galicia; and (iv) HVL for Vestland.

Step 2 – Data collection

Budget for data collection was distributed amongst the four supporting partners, which were responsible for finding relevant companies to perform data collection at regional level. It was not possible to find a single company that could deliver the numbers at regional level for all cases, therefore, a different local company was selected for each case. In order to be able to meet our KPIs (2,000 responses per region) and given the price variations between the four regions, the consortium agreed that responses would be collected through randomly picked online panels when the budget was not possible to cover 2,000 responses using CATIs. Online panel data collection processes were used for the cases of Overijssel, Galicia and Vestland, whereas CATIs were used for Kriti. In all cases, random sampling methods were used keeping the representativeness of our samples in terms of gender. Local survey companies were responsible only for the collection of responses, and not for the data cleansing or the analysis.

The overall period of the data collection took place from June to September 2020 and covered four EU regions: Kriti (GR), Overijssel (NL), Galicia (ES) and Vestland (NO).

Step 3 – Data analysis

Once the local survey companies filled in the regional quotas, the supporting partners provided WR the primary data. WR then performed a concise cleansing of the data, during which corrupt or inaccurate records were detected and subsequently corrected or removed from the datasets. Given the fact that different companies were used for data collection in each region, WR did not merge the collected data into a unified dataset, but kept the analysis at regional level. This was also done to keep the regional specificities in the analysis, since RRI and regional dilemmas are concepts that are perceived and experienced differently in each regional context. In Section 4, a comparative approach between the different regions is followed, after having thoroughly described the structure of the regional samples in Tables 1 and 2.

Step 4 – Discussion of the findings

After completing the analysis of the survey, WR presented internally the main findings of the data analysis to all project partners in a dedicated virtual meeting on January 22nd, 2021. There, all partners (including the 4 pilot regions) had the chance to discuss the results and investigate the ways that they can be further exploited in future steps of the RRI2SCALE project.